

STUDY OF FACIAL PAIN IN A PRACTICE OF DENTIST**Farxatov Sunatilloxon Furkatovich****Axmedov Alisher Astanovich****Samarkand State Medical University**

Annotation: In clinical practice, dentists and neurologists often face facial pain of varying severity, local and duration. The various etiologies and pathologies of pain, summarized by the term "facial pain", reflect the anatomy and physiology of the autonomic and somatic nerves of the facial tissues. Differential diagnosis is very difficult and is often misdiagnosed. Dental diseases, especially those related to teeth, are one of the most common causes of facial pain. Pain in such cases always occurs in the same area of the face (Zaharinin-gedazone). The nasolabial folds correspond to the canines of the upper jaw and the premolars of the upper right jaw, while the buccal area near the alar (maxillary zone) corresponds to the second maxillary premolars and the upper right jaw premolars. The temporal region corresponds to the first maxillary molars, and the lower jaw corresponds to the second and third maxillary molars. The sublingual region corresponds to the first and second mandibular molars. Ear pain is usually present in the area of the lower jaw molars and in the area of the upper jaw molars in front of the thyroid gland. The third mandibular molars correspond to the protrusions of the larynx at the leading edge of the sternocleidomastoid muscle. The incisors, canines and first premolars of the lower jaw correspond to the upper jaw region. Reflex facial pain does not always occur, but appears a few hours after the onset of toothache. After tooth extraction, the pain in the corresponding area disappears after 24 hours. Reflex pain can occur in the Zaharinin-gedazone even if there is no pain in the affected tooth. With proper diagnosis and treatment of the affected tooth, the pain in the corresponding area will completely disappear. Pain in the anterior upper jaw can also be observed with

defects in dentures caused by occlusal disorders. Occlusal disorders associated with tooth defects cause changes in all components of the temporomandibular joint, causing compression of the tympanic nerve and pain in the face, tongue and ears. Disorders of the temporomandibular joint often occur in the form of myofascial pain dysfunction of muscle origin associated with overload of certain muscles. In recent years, 70% of back pain syndromes have been attributed to myofascial causes. Myofascial disorders of the facial muscle system occur in the same mechanism as in the skeletal muscle system. 10-20% of facial pain syndromes are caused by myofascial disorders. The mechanism of myofascial pain is that residual tension occurs in the muscles in the early stages, followed by persistent local muscle hypertension. Such local muscle hypertension can cause short-term muscle spasms (seizures). For example, the chewing muscles can twitch, causing pain when opening your mouth or yawning. In addition, such muscle hypertension often causes persistent muscle tension, which leads to chronic pain. Persistent local muscle hypertension is a secondary disorder (blood vessels, metabolism, inflammation) in spasmodic muscles. In the case of tumors of the occipital fossa, the roots of the trigeminal nerve may be squeezed. There is a hypothesis that a tumor in the occipital fossa compresses the roots of the trigeminal nerve, or that the nerve is compressed by loop-like vessels (usually the upper cerebral and lower cerebellar arteries). The central mechanism of pain attacks is activated for the second time under the influence of pathological afferent effects from the periphery. This manifests itself as an attack of sharp and intense pain in the area dominated by the trigeminal nerve. With secondary (symptomatic) trigeminal neuralgia due to lesions of the trigeminal nerve due to tumors, atypical symptoms appear already in the early stages of the disease. The disease is more common in the elderly. The attack of pain is localized in the ruling area of the branches of the trigeminal nerve and lasts from a few seconds to a few minutes, its intensity is likened to "gunfire" or lightning strikes. These are characterized by the presence of "trigger" zones, plant

neurological symptoms (lacrimation, hyperemia, hyperhidrosis, nasal bleeding (affected side), increased salivation and painful tics).Seizures often occur in the morning in the autumn-winter period.Glossopharyngeal neuralgia (Shikar's syndrome) occurs as a result of damage to the tonsils bed, such as an extension of the tongue protrusion or carotid aneurysm.This condition is common under the age of 50.It is characterized by burning paroxysmal pain that lasts from a few seconds to 3 minutes.The localized site of pain is the root of the tongue, the palatine tonsils, the mandibular angle, the anterior part of the parotid gland.The surrounding zones are the tonsils, the root of the tongue and the parotid gland.During a seizure, the patient is unable to speak or swallow saliva, takes an impossible posture, for example, tilts his head to the affected side.A strong laryngeal cough occurs after a seizure.The diagnostic test for Shikar's syndrome is the administration of anesthetics during anesthesia of the pharyngeal mucosa or palpation in the oral cavity.Pterygeal ganglion neuralgia (Sluder's syndrome) is a painful sore throat of the autonomic nervous system that occurs as a result of damage to this node and is associated with paroxysmal autonomic dysfunction.The etiology of the disease is not exactly established, but mechanical, allergic, mental and other factors are important.The curvature of the nasal septum is often detected.It is believed that local pathological processes play the main role in the development of lesions in this section.Common infections, allergies, somatic and mental factors are important.The occurrence of bouts of pain with local vasomotor disorders is associated with the release of serotonin, histamine, quinine, and stimulation of nodes and their connections.Stimulation of nerve mechanisms and the accumulation of biological amines in the blood cause the development of systemic autonomic vascular reactions (dizziness, nausea).Based on the above, the disease can be divided into local and systemic forms.Paroxysmal pain can last from minutes to hours or even days.The pain can be persistent or increase paroxysmal.The aggravation can last for weeks or months. Dysesthesia, characterized by increasing

frequency and duration, can last from months to years and is influenced by various local and general factors. Local causes of glossodynia include mechanical injuries, allergic reactions to dental appliances, and chemical irritants. General causes encompass chronic gastrointestinal diseases, diabetes, menopausal disorders, and auriculotemporal syndrome, which manifests as pain in the temple, ear, or jaw, often triggered by eating or stress. Parotemporal syndrome may arise from complications of mumps affecting the parotid gland, leading to disrupted salivation. Rarely, gangliosis of submandibular and sublingual segments occurs due to trauma or inflammation, causing persistent pain and hyperalivation. The disease often presents with mucosal changes on the tongue, taste disorders, and psychological symptoms.

In conclusion: facial pain syndromes have diverse origins and require thorough diagnosis to differentiate between local and systemic causes, particularly neurological conditions.

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